

TEACHING SPEAKING ENGLISH AT THE BEGINNING STAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article studies about how to teach speaking English for beginners and about some methods and approaches for teaching elementary level students. It is vital to mention that the work is devoted to highlight the effects of some techniques to improve learners' speaking skill.

The teaching and learning of speaking are a vital part of any language education classroom; not only does the spoken language offer 'affordances' for learning as the main communicative medium of the classroom, but it is also an important component of syllabus content and learning outcomes. However, teaching speaking remains challenging for many teachers. A key issue here is whether what happens in a speaking classroom is concerned with 'doing' teaching or 'teaching' speaking. In this paper, I consider some of the essential elements that comprise speaking competence and offer a teaching-speaking cycle designed to address the teaching of speaking systematically. The paper finishes with a brief analysis of the key aspects of the teaching-speaking cycle, identifying how it covers areas that are central to planning a holistic and sequenced approach to the teaching of speaking.

Comments such as the following are familiar to many teachers working

in classrooms which aim to develop speaking skills: All my students can read and write well, but they are poor at speaking and listening. Many of my students are too afraid to talk in class. They are shy and lack confidence. Some of my students sound very "bookish" when they speak – it's as if they are reading from a book! My students love to speak, but they make a lot of grammatical mistakes. These kinds of observations are not surprising, as learning to speak in another language is a challenging undertaking. Speaking is a highly complex and dynamic skill that involves the use of several simultaneous processes – cognitive, physical and socio-cultural – and a speaker's knowledge and skills have to be activated rapidly in real-time. It is important, therefore, that speaking should be taught explicitly in

language classrooms – simply “doing” speaking activities is not the same as learning the knowledge, skills and strategies of speaking. By way of illustration, we will consider the following classroom situation:

Teacher M realized from early in her career that it was important to

develop her students’ speaking abilities. She wanted to make sure that her students had plenty of opportunities to communicate with one another in English, so she set aside two lessons a week for speaking practice. She planned many interesting activities for her students. Her lessons were carefully guided by instructional objectives. These objectives were in the form of either what the students should produce (e.g. presentations, debates, descriptions) or what they had to do (e.g. discuss, narrate, role play). Sometimes when they had finished the activities, Teacher M would ask them to present the outcomes to the rest of the class. At other times she would simply move on to another activity, such as reading or writing.

In several ways, Teacher M was successful in constructing her speaking lessons. However, there were also limitations regarding how directly she was addressing the students’ needs to improve their speaking. On the positive side, she presented a variety of activities, which could appeal to her students’ different learning styles. Clearly, her students enjoyed interacting during the lesson and the activities gave them opportunities to practice speaking. They also had some opportunities to present the outcomes of the activities. Less positively, however, the lessons provided little preparation for

practicing specific speaking skills, and they lacked any explicit teaching of key features of speaking. The students were not encouraged to give attention to knowledge, skills, or strategy development. Also, there was little feedback on their performance, and minimal or no follow-up to the activities. What must a competent speaker be able to do? To teach speaking holistically and comprehensively, it is valuable for teachers to be knowledgeable about what speaking competence involves and how different aspects of speaking competence relate to each other. Johnson (1996: 155) describes speaking as a “combinatorial skill” that “involves doing various things at the same time”. Figure 1 below presents a model of second language speaking competence that comprises knowledge of language and discourse, core speaking skills, and communication

and discourse strategies. Learning to speak in a second language involves

increasing the ability to use these components in order to produce spoken

language in a fluent, accurate and socially appropriate way, within the constraints of a speaker’s cognitive processing. Strategies, involves developing cognitive strategies to compensate for limitations in language knowledge (e.g. circumlocution, paraphrasing, gestures, word coinage, approximation, avoidance), metacognitive strategies (e.g. planning in advance what to say, thinking consciously about how you say something), and interaction strategies (e.g. asking for clarification/repetition, reformulating, rephrasing, and checking comprehension). What this model implies is that speaking lessons are not just occasions for practicing or “doing” speaking. They

need to be conceptualized as structured and supported learning opportunities for developing these various

components of speaking competence. It is important that teachers guide

learners systematically, introducing activities that are integrated and sequenced and that allow students to raise their awareness of the knowledge, skills and strategies needed for various types of interaction and discourse.

Students may need guidance on specific aspects of the language, such as

Pronunciation features, either at segmental or suprasegmental level, or they may need support in relation to affective factors, such as anxiety, nervousness or embarrassment about speaking in another language. Many approaches typically used in language teaching to teach speaking have taken little account of the nature of spoken language, and have tended instead to fall back on grammars that are essentially based on written text. Technological advances in recording speech and the establishment by linguists of corpora of speech utterances have led to much greater knowledge about the similarities and differences between these two modes of communication. It is very valuable for language teachers to be aware of some of the main differences and of the features that typically characterize speech, as this will allow them to make more informed decisions about what to teach. McCarthy (1998: 79–80) makes the point that: Anyone who has looked at large amounts of informal spoken data, for example, cannot fail to be struck by the absence of well-formed 'sentences' with main and subordinate clauses. Instead we often find turns that are just phrases, incomplete clauses, clauses that look like subordinate clauses but which seem not to be attached to any main clause, etc. Although spoken and written languages

are clearly related, typically they serve different social purposes and have different audiences. Speakers and writers draw on common linguistic resources, but they utilize them in different ways; as Halliday (1985: 45) notes, "... the kinds of meanings that are transmitted in writing tend to be somewhat different from the kinds of meanings transmitted through speech". By way of illustration, compare the following texts that deal with the same content and meanings. The speaker in Text 1 is describing the experience of studying in a Master's course offered as a distance learning program. Text 1 I was working in Turkey at the time... um I was lucky enough to have one of my colleagues doing the same program... started at the same time as me so we used to get together regularly...er sometimes as often as twice a week and would get together and compare our

findings and...er because our learning styles were different as well, we, well, compensated for one another other...

Text 2 illustrates how this information might be expressed in a written

version.

Text 2

I was then employed in Turkey, where fortunately I was able to collaborate with a colleague who commenced the program simultaneously. We held regular weekly meetings to compare findings. Because our learning styles were different, we complemented each other. There are some noticeable differences in the way the meanings are 'packaged' in these two texts. Speech is constructed spontaneously and therefore shows particular patterning of language use that are not usually found in written texts. Table 1 below summarizes some of the key differences between the spoken and written language. It is important to note

that these differences broadly typify these differences; speech and writing may

be more or less typically spoken-like or written-like depending on the sociocultural context, the topic, the relationships between speaker/writer and listener/reader and the distance in time and space from the phenomena, events or actions which are the focus of meaning.

Another useful insight for language teachers who teach speaking relates

to social and functional motivation for speaking. The distinction has long been made between interpersonally motivated speech and pragmatically motivated speech (Brown & Yule 1983). Pragmatic or transactional talk involves exchanging information or goods and services (e.g. seeking information about a job, calling an ambulance) with the purpose of getting things done in daily life. Interactional or interpersonal talk, on the other hand, is primarily directed towards creating and maintaining social relationships (e.g. chatting with friends or family, making small talk). These distinctions are useful because they enable teachers to identify

which major kinds of interactions are important for their students. However, in practice most spoken interaction is a mixture of both social and functional

motivation: it would be surprising for business meetings not to involve elements of interpersonal talk, even though the main purpose is primarily transactional. However, these elements would be constrained by the speakers' awareness of the main purpose of needing to get the business done and the typically more formalized roles and relationships among the speakers. Similarly, a casual conversation between friends, which is mainly interactional, might contain episodes where the purpose is transactional, such as asking for information about a technical matter or negotiating a price for goods being purchased. Spoken language typically foregrounds interpersonal relationships in a way that is usually less common in written texts, so that the nature of the relationships between speakers inevitably

has an impact on how they select language. Speakers take into account their evaluations of differences such as their relative social power, status or expertise, emotional, or affective, distance or closeness, and the extent of regular contact they maintain.

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